

DISCO Innovation Machine

“Towards Sustainable Aviation” Summit - TSAS 2022
18-20 October 2022

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AIRBUS

Airbus Autonomy Landscape

Airbus Amber

SAFETY
DISCO
INNOVATION
CO₂
SUSTAINABILITY
DISRUPTIVE COCKPIT

A purpose: continuous safety enhancement

Airbus Amber

10 year moving average fatal accident rate (per million flights) per aircraft generation

DISCO Innovation Machine - TSAS 2022 - October 2022

Innovation in technology contributed to the reduction of accident rates

www.accidentstats.airbus.com

A purpose: continuous safety enhancement

Airbus Amber

Average fatal accident rate (per million flights) per accident category 1958-2021

Controlled Flight Into Terrain

Loss Of Control In-flight

Runway Excursion

Automation
Perception
Navigation
Human-Machine Interface

www.accidentstats.airbus.com

A purpose: continuous safety enhancement

How to go even further?

TCAS: Traffic Collision Avoidance System

Ideation Process

- Build a team, cooperate
 - All Airbus entities, Acubed, ONERA, DLR ... Thales, Honeywell ...
 - Eurocontrol, DSNA, DFS ... Airlines ... EASA ...
 - Supporting Agencies: DGAC, Clean Sky JU ...
- Sand box
 - start from a clean sheet
 - tools and means to iterate quickly
- “Shoot the Moon” - aim at a very ambitious (possibly unattainable) target:
 - Enhance safety margins
 - Enable Single Pilot Operations
 - Reduce recurring cost ... weight, drag counts ...
 - Consistent with Airbus cockpit philosophy
- To propose radical solutions and breakthrough technologies

*Give time and data
in all conditions
to assess the situation
and make a good decision*

Process Outcome

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Team **engagement**.

Promising **safety improvements**

- baseline for a new development
- incremental improvements explored

If market pull ... **Single Pilot Operations** could be investigated further, for safe introduction

Thank you.

[Airbus Amber]

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